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Some Contributing Factors to the Modernity of Late Nineteenth and Early Twentieth Century's Chinese Calligraphy and Paintings

Jingwei Zeng

Abstract

This paper explores some factors that gave rise to the modernity of late nineteenth and early twentieth century Chinese calligraphy and painting from the University of Wisconsin-Milwaukee's Special Collections. The art in this period has long been signified as a cultural stagnation. However, its modernist tendency is demonstrated here, bringing the overlooked subjects to the forefront of twenty-first century scholarship. By establishing a broad stylistic spectrum characteristic of its calligraphy and paintings, this paper challenges the long-established terms of "tradition" and "modernity" used to define Chinese *fin-de-siècle* art: instead of seeing these artistic creations as mutually exclusive concepts with fixed characteristics, it recalibrates and redefines them as modern categories influenced by literary innovations, vernacularization and westernization, and iconoclasm from the late Ming Dynasty.

Key Words

Late Qing, early twentieth-century, modernity, calligraphy, painting

Introduction

Few moments in Chinese history can have been as tumultuous and complicated as that between the late Qing Dynasty (1840-1912) and the early years of the Republic (1912-1928), a time during which China was continually battered by foreign encroachment and internal conflict, and Chinese intellectuals seemed to have lost their traditional foundation.¹ This instability became a cradle for inclusive cultures, as the intellectuals gained more opportunities to reevaluate the old and interpret the new.² In light of this, the late Qing's art prompts us to deconstruct the previously prevailing binaries between tradition and modernity, and motivates us to understand how modern the artistic discourse was and how accommodating the Chinese cultural repertoire was at that crucial historical moment.³

Like German paintings of the same period, the *fin-de-siècle* Chinese art languished in obscurity in both China and the Western historiography.⁴ For instance, in *The History of the Qing's Painting*, Xue Yongnian asserted that the slavish imitations of ancient masters undermined

the creativity and individuality of the late Qing artists.⁵ James Cahill (1926-2014) indicated that the increasing practice of simplified paintings was the most noticeable cause for the decline of Chinese painting after the early Qing period.⁶ Moreover, the art made by the Yilao ("leftover," i.e., for those loyal to the fallen regime) is ruthlessly dispatched to historical oblivion, having their reputations entangled with the degenerate images of the feudal dictatorship.⁷

However, propelled by a strong rhythmic cadence pulsating throughout the era, the arts were modern, open, cacophonous, and blossoming in a wide range of genres: in calligraphy, the Model-book School, Stele School, Model-cum-Stele School, Jinshixue (antiquarianism) and Qiwuxue (the study of three-dimensional antiquities) coexisted in harmony; in painting, the Orthodox School, Jinshi (metal-and-stone) School, Literati Painting School, vernacular painting, and Western-style all contributed to the boom in *fin-de-siècle* art. The cornucopia of various genres signaled the beginning of Chinese artistic modernization.

This artistic efflorescence was derived from the robust

Figure 1. Lin Shu, *Landscape Painting of Chao Lake*, the late Qing Dynasty and early Republic of China, paper, 18"×73.3", Special Collections, University of Wisconsin-Milwaukee Libraries, Milwaukee, digital identification cs000110.

economic, social, and political advancements of the period. As people had more opportunities for education, business, communication, transportation, and freedom to pursue individuality, they congregated for organizations, supported reforms, translated foreign publications, and caught up with the leitmotif of the world. To some degree, these advancements were reflected in the artistic creations, as artists were active in critiquing old traditions, inspiring new ideas, and helping to form a revolutionary spirit of Chinese modernity. This is like turn-of-the-century German painting, which encompasses both tradition and modernism, and therein demonstrates the “Spirit of the Age.”⁸

This turn-of-the-century modernity could be reflected through the visual and material nature of Chinese calligraphy and paintings from the Special Collections in the library at the University of Wisconsin-Milwaukee (UWM), donated by Professor Zhou Cezong (1916-2007) and his wife Nancy Wu Chow. On April 13, 2023, *Open Parameters—Late Nineteenth and Early Twentieth Century’s Chinese Calligraphy and Paintings from the Zhou Cezong Donation* was presented in The Emile H. Mathis Gallery at UWM, showing artworks with various styles to demonstrate the little-appreciated intellectual and artistic liberalism of that period.

Based on this exhibition and the UWM library’s Special Collections, this paper demonstrates that the literary innovations, vernacularization and westernization, and the iconoclasm from the late Ming Dynasty are the important factors contributing to the modernity of the late nineteenth and early twentieth century’s calligraphy and paintings. The trends from literary inventions, the life of the middle class, imports of the West, and the strong individuality inherited from the late Ming broadened the literati art, which once only belonged to cultural elites, to the enjoyment of the public. Most importantly, they picked up momentum for the artists to resonate with the socio-political advancements and take a stand against the tempestuousness of the age.

1. The Influence of Literary Modernism

In literature, according to the May Fourth paradigm, late Qing fiction was merely the end of the old tradition and the beginning of Western influence, following a singular path of evolution.⁹ However, publications on Chinese literature which discuss modernity and innovation have proliferated since the 1990s.¹⁰ For instance, David Der-wei Wang’s seminal publication *Fin-de-siècle Splendor: Repressed Modernities of Late Qing Fiction, 1849-1911*, noted that the late Qing’s literary inventions had developed a “complex matrix of incipient modernities,”

exhibiting a strong inclination to create something original and different.¹¹ Guo-ou Zhuang indicated that the nostalgia for the old and the embrace of modernity reflect Chinese consciousness to partake in a relationship with the world.¹² Andrew F. Jones evaluated this modernity from the perspective of cultural evolution, from which he asserted that the Chinese modernistic achievements in recent decades were founded in the late nineteenth century.¹³ These arguments also ring true for the modernism of Chinese art. From UWM's collection, we can see how the literary innovations, such as the spirit of originality, poetic simile, and combination of old and new influenced the artistic creations in this period, working in tandem with each other as the precursor of the Chinese modernist movement.

Lin Shu (1852-1924) was one of the most pioneering literati in modern Chinese history to generate a modern identity by adopting literary innovation. Though he did not know a word of a foreign language, he translated hundreds of foreign novels under the auspices of his collaborators.¹⁴ By frequent snipping, polishing, and even defamiliarizing the original texts,¹⁵ his translations unleashed a new creative force for Chinese modern literature. In addition, though Lin adopted classical Chinese for his translation, he preferred a free and elegant style, which was accessible to the public, and could be regarded as a literary creation per se.¹⁶ The coexistence of Western literature and free translation imbues his works with a palpable global consciousness, from which he gave his readers and even Chinese modern literature a cosmopolitanism. Lin was often named a Yilao; however, when studied under the proper light, his experiment would prove instrumental in a "translated modernity," betokening modern human experience and shedding light on the ways in which readers internalize the idea of modernity with personal expression.¹⁷

Lin Shu's *Chao Lake* greatly manifests his sense of modernity (figure 1). According to the inscription, the painting was inspired by Jiang Kui's (1155-1221) *Manjianghong* (*The Whole River Red*), a Ci poem depicting people celebrating the birthday of the deity of Chao Lake.¹⁸ However, unlike other literati-painters who preferred to write down the lengthy ancient poem verbatim as the inscription, Lin made his short poem in plain language, indicating that there is no extra space for the ancient. Similarly, though he admitted the bravura of deity in this poem, he suggested it is dwarfed by the virtuosity of Ci composer Jiang and painter Lin who could record the event and perpetuate the scenery. Here, the power of the deity and the beauty of the scenery could not come to life except in the guise of Lin's literary

Figure 2. Chen Sanli, *Facing to the Rain in the Residence of Mountain*. The late Qing Dynasty and early Republic of China, paper, 15"×76", Special Collections, University of Wisconsin-Milwaukee Libraries, Milwaukee, digital identification cs000102.

and pictorial creation. Lin transcended the boundaries of literature and art by simplifying the language, defamiliarizing the original texts, and intimating an attitude of authority, thereby creating a cubist style and modernist perception.¹⁹

Chen Sanli (1852-1937) was another master spear-heading the promotion of literary modernism. As the leader of the Tong-Guang Poetic Style, Chen was criticized by Hu Shi (1891-1962) due to the usage of obscure literary allusion in his poems.²⁰ However, scholars since his time have noticed that the recondite feature in his poem was his proclamation to resist the degeneration of poetic mimesis.²¹ As claimed by Liu Na,

by choosing words and expressions that were abstruse to the public, Chen expressed his yearning for freedom.²² Tsung-Cheng Lin expanded this espousal by indicating Chen's poetic innovations not only conveyed his psychological state, but also "resonate(d) with themes found in modern literature."²³ In the last sentence of this scroll (figure 2), "Rains dampen the wings of a solitary eagle, but it will still soar to the sunset," Chen used the word sunset to create a sensation of evanescence, feebleness, and disorientation, evoking the traumatic experiences of his unfulfilled career and his father's death,²⁴ but also reverberating with the incipient sense of modernism in his time. As two of the most eminent Chinese reformers of the nineteenth century, Chen Sanli and his father Chen Baozhen (1831-1900) worked together to press a thoroughgoing program of reform in Hunan Province from 1895 to 1898. Their provincial success won accolades in the nation, encouraging the emperor to implement the reforms nationwide.²⁵ After the reform was repressed in 1898, Chen and his father were dismissed.²⁶ The well-established laws and legislations, which were stipulated by the father and son in a "laborious and sinuous" effort and proven effectual in many aspects of the reform, were "eradicated without a trace."²⁷ Most poignantly, Chen's father was subsequently granted

suicide by the imperial order.²⁸ Afterwards, Chen found solace in Chinese literature, expressing his "depressive indignation and upright passion."²⁹

The poetic simile used in the word sunset is worth looking at. Sunset is often indicative of the captivating beauty of nature, but here, it also connotes the doldrums and negativity, reflecting Chen's bewilderment in the face of modernization. It is at once simple and complex, alluring and heart-wrenching. Similarly, when one looks at Chen's calligraphy, they would first be enthralled by the simple beauty of his art, as almost every character was created with equal size and permuted with the same space. However, by careful examination, the work is overwhelmed by somberness and intensity. Denoting a sepulchral fashion, the calligraphy reflects shadows of bodies that look wounded or butchered, conjuring up the vicissitude of life and the complexity of history.

The equal-spaced and heavy-handed permutation in this calligraphy is redolent of the gruesome wall-building homicide in Edgar Allan Poe's (1809-1849) *The Cask of Amontillado* (1846), and the racially charged vignette in Kara Walker's *Endless Conundrum, An African Anonymous Adventuress* (2001, figure 3). Each of Chen's characters bears a resemblance to each brick in Poe's story and each silhouette of Walker's tableaux. Though

Figure 3. Kara Walker, *Endless Conundrum, An African Anonymous Adventuress*, 2021, cut paper on wall, 191"×453" (485.1×1150.6 cm). Installation view from *Kara Walker: My Complement, My Enemy, My Oppressor, My Love*, ARC/Musée d'Art Moderne de la Ville de Paris, 2007. Photo: Florian Kleinfenn ©Kara Walker, courtesy of Sikkema Jenkins & Co. and Sprüth Magers.

the accumulation of similar components looks simple and formulaic, it consistently thrusts upon us convulsive shudders and complex sensations, giving forth an aura of penetrating seriousness to those unsettled problems that make modern society split asunder: tyranny, racism, and human folly. Here, calligraphy was created in sync with the modern spirit of criticism, reflectivity, and satirization, grounding modernity in a conscious attention to the self and disorientation of sociopolitical discourse.

2. The Influence of Vernacularization and Westernization

In the late nineteenth and early twentieth centuries, Chinese society was profoundly transformed from agrarian to increasingly urban and mercantile. In the new society, a growing urban middle class, affluent and eager to adopt a more sophisticated lifestyle, constructed a vastly expanding market for the works and services of vernacular art, literature, and entertainment.³⁰ In this context, vernacular paintings flourished.³¹ Since vernacular painters were required to satisfy the needs and desires of their clientele, and since these desires were so diverse and flexible, they enjoyed considerable freedom by exploring the real world around them far more freely than their prestigious contemporaries could do.³² By bringing forth subjectivity, vernacular spirit responds to and engages with the features of social modernity, which, in Miriam Hansen's (1949-2011) words, produces a new sensorium for the "vernacular modernism."³³

Ji Yue's *Sending off Penury* (figure 4) represents the morality inherent in vernacular art. It comes from a renowned eponymous essay by Han Yu (768-824), associated with the Chinese custom of casting off old clothes on the last day of the first lunar month to persuade the Demon of Penury to leave. In Ji's painting, Han Yu clasps his hands together and offers his thanks to the statuette of the Demon of Penury, as he prepares to send it away. The Demon of Penury is characterized by five apparitions of penury (qiong, which means deprivation or paucity): intellect, learning, penmanship, luck, and friendship. According to Han, the moral, eclectic, original, altruistic, and sincere characteristics, which scholars cherish, are unfortunately irrelevant to practical usage. To a certain degree, these characteristics ipso facto deprive scholars of access to intellect, learning, penmanship, luck, and friendship, preventing them from being successful.³⁴ The lively scene between an unsuccessful literatus and apparitions in this painting can be regarded much more like a self-proclamation than

Figure 4. Ji Yue, *Sending off Penury*, ca. 1884, silk, 15.7"×17", Special Collections, University of Wisconsin-Milwaukee Libraries, Milwaukee, digital identification cs000120.

a self-satirization, implying that Chinese literati would adhere to the moralities even when inflicted with woe and injustice. The resignation on Han's face indicates a common malaise shared by these literati and the country, but the untrammelled spirit embodied in the five apparitions reassures them that their achievements will be recognized eventually in the long annals of history. Grasping this ineffable and figurative reality is the exquisite product of illumination transporting audiences to a universe where every detail is inseparable from its tangible world, but higher than that world in aesthetics. In this respect, vernacular painting works as a sobering reminder of morality, aiming at a broader resonance of modern life.

Vernacular painting could also be regarded as an emotional appeal to the prospect of modernization and thus interwoven with political imperative. In 1897, Qiu Tingliang (1857-1943) urged the vernacularization of the traditional language, indicating it would not only help people to receive new ideas, but also carry a "key to reform."³⁵ In art, vernacularism was also adopted in consonance with socio-political valence, which could be seen in *Wang Xizhi's Exchange Calligraphy for Geese* painted by Zhou Xun (figure 5).

It is said that Wang Xizhi (306-361), one of the most famous Chinese calligraphers, was greatly fond of geese because of their unique neck movement. Hearing that there was a Taoist monk who raised a flock of superior geese, Wang went to his house and asked to purchase some. Knowing Wang was a prominent calligrapher, the monk proposed exchanging the geese for one of Wang's

Figure 5. Zhou Xun, *Wang Xizhi's Exchange Calligraphy for Geese*, the late Qing Dynasty, silk, 21.5"×60", Special Collections, University of Wisconsin-Milwaukee Libraries, Milwaukee.

calligraphy works. Without further ado, Wang finished the writing and brought the geese home.³⁶ Drawing from this legend, Zhou's painting exudes great charm and camaraderie. However, coarseness and tension also prevail in the painting. While Wang is shown wielding the brush, he is not writing anything down on the paper, implying a perfunctory simplicity. In addition, the table does not have any adornment, and the terrain is barren. The inherent business-like coarseness indicates the predicament of late Qing society. Though the reforms

created some progress, they were executed shoddily, failing eventually because of domestic disorder and foreign intrusion.³⁷ Worth mentioning is the compressed scene of the painting. With so many components jostling for position in a tiny space, the painting is full of tension and anxiety. The tension is amplified by the image painted on the screen, where a huge swirling spume dashes toward the red rising sun. While the wave and sun symbolize prosperity and vitality, they imply an overture of clashing noise and angst, suggestive of the seething tension in society, and work as a prognostication of radicalization and conflict throughout the twentieth century. In these two paintings, vernacularism is strongly connected with the sociopolitical context, not only suggesting the customs, legends, and experiences of daily life but also making an oblique reference to the rise and fall of the dynasty.

Besides the vernacular spirit, the leitmotif of Westernization is also the catalyst for the late Qing's artistic modernity. In 1895, the court terminated the imperial examination, which gave legitimacy and authority to Western learning.³⁸ Men of foresight began to realize that studying the military and industrial techniques from the West was not enough to move the country forward. Alternately, they called for the studies of Western politics, economy, science, social structure, philosophy, and even art and literature.³⁹ Against this backdrop, even the most traditional artists would be aware of the enchanting beauty and scientific precision of imported paintings.⁴⁰ The heterogeneity from the Western paintings inadvertently, even if passively, redefined their artistic idioms, and sucked them into a vortex of cross-cultural exchange.⁴¹ The prevalence of Western art incentivized some prominent Chinese literati-artists such as Zheng Wuchang (1894-1952) and Feng Zikai (1898-1975) to compare and contrast art in a trans-continental fashion and formed an inclusive sense of cosmopolitanism.⁴²

In this period, the artistic patronage in the port cities thrived concurrently with the intensifying exchange of East and West.⁴³ Against this background, European art offered a new style to satisfy this patronage. Some Chinese traditional painters quickly added this style into their repertoire.⁴⁴ From 1902 until 1931, Wang Zhen worked as a comprador for Japanese companies such as the Osaka Shipping Corporation and the Nisshin Steamship Corporation.⁴⁵ As one of the most influential contributors to prewar Sino-Japanese artistic exchange,⁴⁶ Wang had many opportunities to connect with Japanese and Western paintings. Standing at this crucial inflection point, his coloristic modeling of the headdress and robe in figure 6 exhibits the rich palette and superb brush

handling, creating a trompe l'oeil effect which had been a property of Western painting. Meanwhile, Wang infused the calligraphic components into this painting. The outline's dry, scratchy, and swirling traces come from Zhang Xu's (675-750) "wild cursive" script writing, famous for impressive energy, speed, and exaggeration.⁴⁷ In this way, the painting is a perfect example to demonstrate how Western components were adapted and mingled according to local standards and preferences, emerging to a broad readership contemporary to its author.

Placing the elements of the picture on a convincingly receding plane is another European convention commonly practiced by Chinese artists. In Lin Shu's *Summer Landscape* (figure 7), he attempted to create a cloudy mountain scene following the tradition of Gao Kegong (1248-1310). Nevertheless, influenced by Western realism, Lin made certain departures from Gao's convention: the architectonic construction and conspicuous visual contrast between the dense foliage and unpainted space in the middle offer new ways to appreciate a complex composition, challenging the traditional Chinese understanding of three-dimensionality, and exhibiting a cross-national hybridity.

3. The Influence of Late Ming's Iconoclasm

In the field of late imperial China, it is not uncommon to conceptualize the Ming and Qing dynasties as a meaningful period that crossed dynastic timelines. The vital cadence of artistic expression in the late Qing and early Republic period emanated from the cacophonous harmony in the late Ming period (1573-1644). In philosophy, Li Zhi (1527-1602), who was regarded as an "arch-individualist,"⁴⁸ called for genuine expression.⁴⁹ In literature, the rise of the Gonggan School defied the dominance of tradition. In politics, the congregation of Donglin scholars and the formation of the Fushe became the linchpin in the fight for clean politics. In religion, the phenomenon of "Three Teachings (Buddhism, Daoism, and Confucianism)" syncretism led to a pluralism of the cultural movement. In this framework, the established dichotomies such as worldly/otherworldly, orthodox/heterodox, conformist/nonconformist, and even masculine/feminine, were upended and subverted.⁵⁰ The emergence of these different voices in multiple areas contributed to the formation of Chinese modernism.

The strong sense of iconoclasm in this new environment motivated the literati to extremes. The decisive change came when Li Zhi pushed this position to belligerent nonconformity and was outspoken in his attack on established rules and standards. From the late

Figure 6. Wang Zhen, *Tao Qian Plucking Chrysanthemums and Facing Mount South*, 1922, paper, 22"×85.8", Special Collections, University of Wisconsin-Milwaukee Libraries, Milwaukee, digital identification cs000073.

nineteenth to the twentieth century, scholars valorized him as the prophet of the Chinese Enlightenment.⁵¹ In 1900, Liu Kunyi (1830-1902) bravely sabotaged the

Empress Dowager's (1835-1908) scheme to depose the emperor and repudiated her edict to exterminate all foreigners in China.⁵² This extraordinary courage was almost unheard of in Chinese history. Li Wentian (1834-1895) and Yan Xiu (1860-1929) also showed their extraordinary courage to challenge the decree of the court, while Zhang Taiyan (1869-1936) was renowned for his *lèse-majesté*.⁵³ When justice and democracy were at risk, the scholar-officials in this period did not hesitate to follow Li's model of criticizing and challenging the rulership as a form of political dissidence.

Li's iconoclasm was immediately evident in the arts of calligraphy and paintings—from the last decade of the sixteenth century to the end of the Ming Dynasty, the concept of *Qi* (the unbalanced and original) rather than *Zheng* (the balanced and conventional) was in the ascendent.⁵⁴ In the late Qing, the pursuit of *Qi* was transformed into the pursuit of modernity-cum-tradition, which is represented by the calligraphy of Shen Zengzhi (1850-1922), Kang Youwei (1858-1927), Zheng Xiaoxu (1860-1938), and Luo Zhenyu (1866-1940). After Luo

Zhenyu and Wang Guowei (1877-1927) published their famous monograph *Liu Sha Zhui Jian* (*The Lost Wooden Slips Excavated in the Flowing Sand*) in 1914, Shen Zengzhi successfully modeled his work with a primitivized fashion. In figure 8, he created an oblique, angular, and dashing brush force by flicking the brush in a pirouette on the paper, which is reminiscent of *Liu Sha Zhui Jian*'s free-wheeling style (figure 9). To look at this kind of artwork is to immediately see the gestural abstraction of the modern art: by splattering ink on the paper, thrusting the brush with various orientations and cadences, and rendering characters with unexpected forms, the author transformed the composition of characters into kinesthetic expression, effectively conflating the art of gesture with the pictorial structure of the work.

Two important artists in the late Ming (and early Qing) presaged a cultural modernity and artistic individuality for the late Qing's artists. The first figure is Dong Qichang (1555-1636). His art-historical theory of Northern and Southern schools stimulated Ruan Yuan

Figure 7. Lin Shu, *Summer Landscape*, 1919, paper, 26"×52", Special Collections, University of Wisconsin-Milwaukee Libraries, Milwaukee, digital identification cs000075b.

Figure 8. Shen Zengzhi, *Calligraphic Hanging Scroll*, 1921, paper, 24"×85", Special Collections, University of Wisconsin-Milwaukee Libraries, Milwaukee, digital identification cs000037.

Figure 9. Luo Zhenyu and Wang Guowei, *Liu Sha Zhui Jian* [流沙坠简] (*The Lost Wooden Slips Excavated in the Flowing Sand*), 1914, (Shangyu: Luo shi chen han lou, 1914), 46.

(1764-1849) to categorize calligraphers into a southern, Model-book School (Tie Xue) characterized by elegant small-size writing models; and a northern, Stele School (Bei Xue) based on the monumental writing found on engraved bronzes, steles, and cliffsides. Inspired by Ruan, Kang Youwei, in his *Guang Yizhou Shuangji* (*Extended Paired Oars for the Boat of Art*), sanctified the Stele School as the new calligraphic orthodoxy, and validated that Xiongqiang (masculine and strong) was the apex of beauty in Chinese art (figure 10).⁵⁵ According to Aida Yuen Wong, Kang's championing of stele writings was "more than an artistic goal" because "it was a conviction that the whole country of China needed to stand up to political adversaries."⁵⁶ Interpreted as such, Dong's aestheticism was appropriated by Kang to form a modernistic rhetoric.

Compared with other masters who interrelated elements of a pictorial group in a realistic way, Dong's art is more of a construct based on an assembly of schemata, with little or no pretense of being anything like reality.⁵⁷ However, there is an antinomy inherent in his works which is unfaithful for optical perception but remains legible for all (figure 11). Therefore, in close examination, there is a constant sense of vitality and even friction in his paintings, akin to the essence of Cubism. Though his paintings were criticized as unbeautiful and awkward, another way of understanding is to see them as the birth pangs of a new modernism. The seemingly haphazard and overcrowded composition in Yao Hua's (1876-1930) work is resonant with Dong's landscape abstraction; in figure 12, the image created is unlike the peonies we see in nature—the leaves are

Figure 10. Kang Youwei, *Calligraphic Couplet*, early Republic of China, paper, 13"×67", Special Collections, University of Wisconsin-Milwaukee Libraries, Milwaukee, digital identification cs000114.

Figure 11. Dong Qichang, *Landscape After the Old Masters*, 1630, ink on paper, 9 5/8"×6 5/16" (24.4×16 cm), The Metropolitan Museum of Art, New York, accession number 1986.266.5k.

disconnected, the petals and stamen are sketched in a cursory fashion, and the spatial depth is flattened. All these elements force the audience to forget about formal likeness and to become aware of the intrinsic values of the brushwork, such as rhythms, patterns, and variations, which work as a self-reference to the author's effervescence and transcend the commonplace image to the ethereal spirituality.

Fu Shan (1607-1684) was another important figure in inspiring Kang Youwei and other late Qing artists to innovate. His powerful dictum "(I would rather my arts) be clumsy but not dainty, awkward but not charming, deformed but not flippant, spontaneous but not premeditated" exhibited his strong feelings toward individuality and anti-traditionalism (figure 14).⁵⁸ For him, the naturalness in the archaic seal and clerical

writings was like the writing of children, "lacking form and rules of characters, showing a sudden strangeness, exhibiting a sense that cannot be united or separated, and intermingling the topsy-turvy, sparse, and dense."⁵⁹ By contrast, premeditation, craftiness, and fastidiousness are the symbol of "dogs and rats," antithetical to independent thinking.⁶⁰ The overtone of liberation in his statement got more and more self-evident in the late Qing, when Chinese literati felt unable to cope with the challenge of a modernizing world and the onslaught of the West. Antiquarianism, which was tinged with a nostalgia for a more secure and prosperous era, or more broadly, a mightier two-thousand-year Chinese history, was badly needed in a period when all reforms of the empire were questioned, and the purpose of governance was challenged.⁶¹

Figure 12. Yao Hua, *Fan Painting of Peony and Lotus*, the late Qing Dynasty and early Republic of China, silk, 11.8"×21.3", Special Collections, University of Wisconsin-Milwaukee Libraries, Milwaukee, digital identification cs000087.

Figure 13. Liang Qichao, *Calligraphic Couplet*, 1927, paper, 79.9"×19", Special Collections, University of Wisconsin-Milwaukee Libraries, Milwaukee, digital identification cs000008.

The brushwork in Wang Zhen's (1867-1938) *Tao Qian Plucking Chrysanthemums and Facing Mount South* (figure 6) conjures up Fu Shan's advocacy of spontaneity and awkwardness. The interplay of dense and empty spaces, the syncopation of wet and dry textures, and the varying degrees of liquidity expressed through smooth and staccato strokes, articulate an exuberant corporeal gesture and a natural flow of temperament, displaying Fu's theories to their utmost. Impressively, the thick, water-saturated, and blunt outlines are derived from the ancient seal-script masterpiece *Stone Drums* (Shi Gu Wen, 374 BC), exhibiting a natural beauty, suggesting a piercing intensity, and giving this painting a surreal, yet lifelike, feel.

Liang Qichao's couplet (figure 13) is also the echoing voice of Fu Shan's arguments. By hiding the sharpness of his brush tip and revealing an awkward restraint, he captured the boldness of carved strokes and their rough, weathered appearance. Even in his semi-cursive inscription, Liang abandoned the common Model-book School's elegance and leisure, displaying an inner tension and subtle countercurrent. In Charles Baudelaire's (1821-1867) opinion, art's modernity is transitory, fugitive, and contingent, which should be counterbalanced by the eternal and immutable.⁶² By turning their gaze backward to ancient immutable writings, Wang and Liang oriented themselves toward the future, granting their art a modernist expression and reformist ideal. The contemporaneity reflected in this past-future dichotomy reveals a more general tendency in global modernity and gives identity to the imagined modern society.⁶³

4. Conclusion

The urgency in the late Qing propelled people across society to undertake a comprehensive post-mortem on the entrenched cultural and spiritual ideologies.⁶⁴ It also galvanized intellectuals to seek social reconstruction and institutional changes to solve the problem. Under this complex milieu, almost every artist seems to have been a modernist, whether embracing Western technologies and political practices or aiming to strengthen the state through a return to practice of Confucian mores.⁶⁵ With this in mind, the art in this period could not be situated "between two worlds (i.e., old and new)" as it is often portrayed; instead, it was a world unto itself—one of cultural openness and experimentation which exhibits a distinguishable vibe of modernity.⁶⁶ Pivoting on the modernism of Chinese art, this paper reevaluates several influences which effectuate the creativity, individuality, adaptability, sociability, tenacity, and reflexivity in late

Figure 14. Fu Shan, *Poem on the Heavenly Emperor*, ca. 1670s, ink on silk (satin), 112"×18 9/16" (284.5×47.1 cm), mount 148 13/16 × 7 5/16" (378 × 69.3 cm), Princeton University Art Museum, Princeton.

nineteenth and early twentieth century Chinese calligraphy and paintings housed in the UWM library’s Special Collections.

It’s worthy to note that the modernistic influences discussed above could not happen without a strong connection to tradition. Liu Haisu (1896-1994) proclaim-

ed that the old and new in art should be seen from a comparative perspective: the ancient Chinese tradition might have new elements for innovation, while the latest Western fashion might be obsolete due to the vagaries of its value.⁶⁷ On top of this, Tsung-Cheng Lin has a more modernistic understanding to problematize Liu’s perspective: using the classic or conditional language or expression might not necessarily be without modernity, while adopting the plain and vernacular might not be necessarily called modern.⁶⁸ Therefore, the long-established terms such as “tradition” and “modernity” can no longer be seen as mutually exclusive concepts with fixed characteristics, but rather as fluid categories that existed in the vast crucible of cultural choices—choices made available by the time, the hybridity of civilization, and the eagerness to change the world.

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晚清至民國時期中國書畫現代性的形成要素

曾經緯

摘要：為了緩解西方對中國的文化入侵以及國內風起雲湧的革命浪潮，晚清社會在經濟，政治，民主，和學術的現代化進程中取得了巨大的成就。國內外所帶來的危機感引發了中國藝術家對固有的藝術形態進行反思，併促成了百家爭鳴式的現代藝術雛形。這些藝術家對現代化的追求，不管是有意還是無意，都體現了對新事物的採納，展示了他們勇於在悠久的文化價值中進行個性化的開拓，更彰顯了他們的創新能力，適應水準，堅韌精神，以及挑戰複雜社會政治問題的智慧及信心。本文以晚清近代書畫所顯示出的現代性為關紐，討論了幾個促成此現代性的重要元素：文學的創新，世俗化與西洋化，以及晚明的反傳統精神，希望借此從新審視和評估書畫的現代主義，併引發對藝術傳統與現代精神的深入討論。

關鍵詞：晚清；近代；現代性；書法；繪畫